

AFRIMA Model Forecast Performance: An Empirical Study using Naira-Yuan Exchange Rate

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ABSTRACT:

In financial time series and econometrics, some macroeconomic variables exhibit long memory features that may not be best described using short memory models like ARIMA. This paper, however, is structured to compare different fractional integration in AFRIMA forecast performance for the Naira-Yuan exchange rate. The empirical monthly data set used covered the period from January 1981 to December 2022. Fractional integration test are based on the ADF unit root test and the auxiliary autoregressive order three (AAR(3)) order of integration test. Model estimation is support by the Marquart algorithm for calculating least squares estimates and performance comparison is based on the Amaefula forecast criterion (AFC). The result specified that AFRIMA (1, d , 1) where $I(d = 0.07891)$ is more appropriate and has the best forecast performance compared to others. The result also reveals that AFRIMA model yield better and more precise forecasts when fractional integration is closer to zero that is, $I(d \rightarrow 0)$ than when $I(d \rightarrow \frac{1}{2})$. Therefore, AFRIMA models can be useful in studying exchange rate dynamics for risk-averse and risk incline in times of investment and profitability in the long-run.

Keywords: AFRIMA, AFC, Fractional integration, Naira-Yuan exchange rate.

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INTRODUCTION

The concept of fractional integration in ARIMA model is generally known as the autoregressive fractional integrated moving average (AFRIMA) model. The model idea was born out of the fact that many time series variables, most especially, macroeconomic variables, exhibit many long-range dependent characteristics that is neither integrated order zero ($I(0)$) nor integrated order one ($I(1)$) in which many unit root tests are not sensitive to detect. Therefore, the AFRIMA model is designed to represent these series where the value of difference (d) is expressed in fractional value such that $|d| \in (0, 1)$. In the context of AFRIMA, a time series y_t is weakly stationary if $d < 0.5$, but non-stationary if $d > 0.5$. The central difference between ARIMA(p, d, q) and AFRIMA(p, d, q) is the integration parameter ($I(d)$) in ARIMA is purely an integer value ($d = 1$ or 2) for the case of integrated order one ($I(1)$) or order two ($I(2)$), but the integration ($I(d)$) in AFRIMA is only restricted to be a fraction less than unity. AFRIMA model is seen as a long memory process and ARIMA model is viewed as short memory process.

In financial time series and econometrics, it is observed that many macroeconomic variables exhibit long memory features that may not be best described using a short memory model framework, specifically, when the autocorrelation function depicts a hyperbolic decay or tailing off to zero. In the

present study, we will model the Naira-Yuan bilateral exchange rate using AFRIMA (p, d, q) process, considering the importance of accurate forecasting of exchange rate to private, public and multinational investment risk.

Nigeria is one of China's biggest export market and a key investment destination in Africa. Last year, as reported by the Envoy of 20th January 2023, the trade volume between Nigeria and China reached almost \$26bn. This value is three times greater than the trade volume between China and Ghana, four times greater than the trade volume between China and Kenya and six times the trade between China and Cameroon [1]. [2] opined that an accurate predicting of exchange rates is vital for big multinational business units as it improves their overall profitability.

Some research work has been done on modeling exchange for the past decades, but most of these studies have enormously used ARIMA across the globe, but little or no studies have considered long memory time dependent like AFRIMA model. [3] found volatility of stock returns exhibited long memory characteristics and also absolute returns had longer memory effects than variances.

Certain financial decisions made today are based on the likelihood of the prevailing exchange rates in the upcoming period. Hence, exchange rate prediction is central to many foreign financial transactions, such as hedging, speculation and capital budgeting [4].

[5] investigated naira vis-a-viz US dollar exchange rate since 1960, adopting ARIMA model, he found ARIMA (4, 1, 1) most appropriate among all subclasses ARIMA(p, d, q) models that were identified and the forecasts generated were satisfactory and reliable most especially for short lead time point. [6] used a non-seasonal ARIMA model in forecasting Naira per US Dollar exchange rate with a data covering the period of January 1994 to December 2011. The result revealed that, the model ARIMA (1, 2, 1) is the best fit for the data. The essence of an accurate prediction of the exchange rates empirically is because it can provide important information to firms, investors and central banks for assets allocation, risk hedging and in policy formulation [7].

[8] adopted ARIMA model in forecasting the Naira-Dollar exchange rate with monthly data spanning from January 1991 to April 2020 and found that ARIMA (2, 1, 3) is the best fitted model based on Akaike information criterion (AIC). [9] adopted ARIMA in modeling the Naira/1 Rupee exchange rate (NREXR) with a monthly period spanned from January 2008 to December 2020 in Nigeria. Comparing four possible ARIMA (p, 1, q) models using an output-based criterion known as the sum of square deviation forecast criterion (SSDFC), conditioned on the absence of serial correlation on the model residuals. He found that ARIMA (1, 1, 2) model is the best performing model with the smallest SSDFC value.

Model information criteria such as Schwarz Bayesian information criterion (SBIC), Akaike information criterion (AIC), Hannan Quinn (HQ), forecast prediction error (FPE) and output-based forecast criterion (AFC) were compared in identifying an optimal autoregressive integrated moving (ARIMA) model for predicting Naira-Franc exchange rate (NFEXR) using monthly data set spanning from 2008M1 to 2020M12. The result specified that the models chosen by SBIC, AIC, HQ and FPE are inadequate and could not satisfy the condition of no autocorrelation in model residuals, but ARIMA (0, 1, 2) specification, exhibited the minimum value of AFC and satisfying the condition of no autocorrelation in the model residuals is identified as the optimal model he concluded that AFC is apt in model identification [10].

In the present paper, our objectives are as follows; firstly, to compare the behavioral pattern of a fractionally integrated time series variable when d varies between zero and half (i.e $0 < d < 0.5$); secondly, to identify and fit three feasible AFRIMA(p, d, q) models for each predetermined value of d ; thirdly, to compare their forecast performances using an output based performance criterion called Amaefula forecast criterion (AFC) and fit the best performing model.

The remaining part of the paper is organized as follows; section 2 provides the materials and methods used in the study, section 3 presents data analysis and results and section 4 raps with a conclusion.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section describes the materials and methods adopted in the study, such as method of data collection, fractional integrated model, order of integration test, model identification, model comparison and estimation techniques.

Method of Data Collection

The yearly time series data on Naira\1 Chinese Yuan is secondary data documented and published in the Central bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin, and it covers the period from January 1981 to December 2022, constituting 180 time series observations [11].

Autoregressive Fractional Integrated Moving Average (AFRIMA) Model

An ARIMA(p, d, q) model where the difference parameter is restricted to a fractional value such that ($0 < d < 0.5$) is called an AFRIMA model, and it is given as;

$$\alpha(L)\Delta^d x_t = \varpi + \beta(L)\varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta^d = (1-L)^d$, $\alpha(L)$ and $\beta(L)$ are p-and q-order lag polynomials, respectively. ε_t is a white noise, $corr(\varepsilon_t, \varepsilon_s) = 0, t \neq s$ and $E[\varepsilon_t] = \mu$. The stochastic process x_t is both stationary and invertible if all roots of $\alpha(L)$ and $\beta(L)$ lie outside the unit circle and $|d| < 0.5$. When $d \in (-0.5, 0.5)$ and $d \neq 0$, then, ACF of an ARFIMA process decays hyperbolically to zero as $i \rightarrow \infty$, and the rate of decay is much slower rate than the exponential decay of a stationary ARMA process (i.e., $d = 0$).

Order of Integration Test

There are several unit root test in the literature and one of such is the popular augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test. In this study, we will adopt the order of integration test (OIT) introduced by [12] which serves as a simple alternative to the unit root test and is presented in (2) below;

$$\left. \begin{aligned} y_t &= \omega_0 + \phi trend + \sum_{j=1}^3 \beta_j y_{t-j} + a_t \\ y_t &= \omega_0 + \sum_{j=1}^3 \beta_j y_{t-j} + a_t \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

The trend parameter coefficient is given as ϕ and if there is no evidence of trend in the series, it can be omitted as specified in (2) above. The intercept is represented by ω_0 . The a_t is the random error term. The β_1, β_2 and β_3 are the coefficients of the lagged dependent variables. It is expected that for integrated order one(I(1)), the conditions are; $|\beta_1| \geq 1, |\beta_2| < 1, |\beta_3| < 1$ and $\left| \frac{\beta_1}{\beta_2} \right| > 1$ and the null hypothesis for I(1), we have $H_{01} : \beta_1 < 1$ and $H_{11} : \beta_1 \geq 1$. For I(2), it is expected that two out of the three lagged parameters should be greater than or equal to unity. the conditions are; $|\beta_1| > 1, |\beta_2| \geq 1, \left| \frac{\beta_1}{\beta_2} \right| > 1$ and $\left| \frac{\beta_2}{\beta_3} \right| \geq 1$. When the data series is I(2), the null hypothesis $H_{02} : \beta_2 < 1$ and $H_{12} : \beta_2 \geq 1$. For more details on the test, see [12].

Model Identification and Comparison Technique

Just as in the case of ARIMA, the autocorrelation and partial autocorrelation play a central role in long memory model identification. The ACF of an ARFIMA process decays hyperbolically to zero and the PACF cuts off after p^{th} lag depicting an AFRIMA($p, d, 0$). However, if the ACF does not decay hyperbolically to zero, an AFRIMA($0, d, q$) or a mix process may be advocated to be fitted.

Information criteria such as the Akaike information criterion(AIC), Schwarz criterion(SC), residual sum of squares and so on are used in terms of model comparison. However, because we are interested in the output forecast performance of the identified models, we will employ Amaefula forecast criterion which is attributed to [10] and it is of the form;

$$AFC = \sqrt{D^T K^{-1} D} \quad (3)$$

where $D = (y_{t,(l,i)} - \hat{y}_{t,(l,i)})$, $y_{t,(l,i)}$ represents the actual variable values matching the i^{th} position of the forecast values and $\hat{y}_{t,(l,i)}$ denotes the forecast values matching the i^{th} position of the actual values. The lead time is represented by l and K designates the number of generated forecasts and should be logically large. Note that K is always equal to the number of the lead time (l).

Model Estimation Diagnostic Test

The coefficients of AFRIMA are estimated using maximum likelihood or iterative algorithm that calculates least squares estimates. At each iteration, the back forecasts are computed and the sum of square errors (SSE) is calculated. [13] for more details.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results from data analysis in this section include graphical exposition, ADF and AAR(3) OIT for fractional integration, correlogram, model comparison and fitting and forecasting.

Graphical Exposition and Fractional Integration Test

The time series plot of Nigeria naira per 1 Chinese yuan for the period January 1981 to December 2022 is as presented in Figure 1 below;

Figure1. Plot of Naira-Yuan Exchange Rate from 2008M1 to 2022M12

The Naira-Yuan exchange rate shows inconsistent fluctuations with the highest exchange rate in December 2010 (at the rate of 30.22 Naira for 1Yuan) and the lowest in October 2022 (at the tune of 16.11 Naira for 1 Yuan).

The Naira-Yuan exchange rate series is fractionally integrated using some predetermined values of differencing (d) as specified in Table1 and then subjected to a stationarity test using ADF and AAR(3) OIT and the results are summarized in the table below.

Table 1. Variable Stationarity Test for Varying Fractional Differencing

S/N	Fractional difference(d)	ADF test statistic	Prob. Value	AAR(3) OIT parameter values		
				β_1	B_2	B_3
1	0.07891	-2.6020	0.0944	0.9579	-0.0766	0.0099
2	0.09876	-2.6677	0.0817	0.9380	-0.0590	0.0097
3	0.1234	-2.7543	0.0671	0.9135	-0.0384	0.0104
4	0.2345	-3.2248	0.0202	0.8031	0.0396	0.0247
5	0.3456	-3.1267	0.0264	0.6941	0.0938	0.0526
6	0.4567	-3.5749	0.0072	0.5879	0.1255	0.0840
7	0.4789	-3.6932	0.0050	0.5671	0.1291	0.0896
8	0.4890	-3.7507	0.0041	0.5576	0.1304	0.0919
9	0.4912	-3.7635	0.0040	0.5555	0.1307	0.0924

The result reveals that the p-values of the ADF test statistics for serial numbers (4 – 9) are significant under 5% level, implying that the data is stationary for the specified values of fractional differences (d). Serial Numbers 1-3 are not significant under 5% level but significant under 10% level, implying weak stationarity. This finding agrees with that of the AAR(3) OIT result. The value of the focused parameter, that is, β_1 tends to unity as d moves closer to zero. Generally, as the d tends closer to zero, the fractional integration tends to $I(1)$. This result implies that there is weak stationarity as the fractional integrated value shifts closer to zero. The result in Table1 is clearer from the test parameter plots as shown in Figure2 and Figure3 below.

Figure 2. Plot Fractional Integration ($0 < d < 0.5$) for Naira-Yuan Exchange Rate Using ADF Test

Figure 3. Plot Fractional Integration ($0 < d < 0.5$) for Naira-Yuan Exchange Rate Using AAR(3) OIT

The plots in Figure1 and Figure2 show the closer the value of ‘ d ’ is to zero, the closer the fractional integration tends to $I(d = 1)$. This is a scenario of near unit root and that explains the long memory nature of the AFRIMA(p, d, q) model.

ACF and PACF Plots

The plots of the ACF and PACF serve as preliminary identification techniques for ARIMA models and their closed forms.

Figure 4. The Plot of ACF for Naira-Yuan Exchange Rate

Figure 5. The Plot of Partial ACF for Naira-Yuan Exchange Rate

The ACF in Figure 4 indicates a gradual decay to zero. Both the positive and negative spikes all decayed slowly to zero. The PACF has a single significant spike that cuts off the 5% significance limits of the PACF. This implies that an AFRIMA(1, d, 0) is identified. However, we will limit the comparison to two different model orders as presented in Table 2.

Table 2. AFRIMA (p, d, q) Model Comparison Using AFC

S/N	Fractional difference(d)	AFRIMA (p, d, q)	RSS	AIC	AFC	Remark
1	0.07891	(1, d, 0)	197.17	20.3997	3.09894	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
		(1, d, 1)	196.315	21.6175	3.08967*	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
2	0.09876	(1, d, 0)	196.791	20.0534	3.31261	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
		(1, d, 1)	196.324	21.6257	3.30730	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
3	0.1234	(1, d, 0)	196.486	19.7742	3.63003	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
		(1, d, 1)	196.341	21.6413	3.62797	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
4	0.2345	(1, d, 0)	197.345	20.5594	5.47869	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
		(1, d, 1)	196.496	21.7833	5.47806	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
5	0.3456	(1, d, 0)	201.125	23.9746	7.62259	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
		(1, d, 1)	196.796	22.0579	7.61712	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
6	0.4567	(1, d, 0)	206.249	28.5029	9.86861	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
		(1, d, 1)	197.261	22.4828	9.85906	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
7	0.4789	(1, d, 0)	207.227	29.3544	10.3236	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
		(1, d, 1)	197.375	22.5868	10.3136	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
8	0.4890	(1, d, 0)	207.649	29.7206	10.5311	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
		(1, d, 1)	197.429	22.6360	10.5208	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
9	0.4912	(1, d, 0)	197.441	20.6469	10.5660	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48
		(1, d, 1)	207.739	31.7986	10.5763	No residual autocorrelation up to lag48

Note: The symbol “*” marks the best model according to AFC. Note that AFC is computed with lead time ($l = 150$), the forecast origin is 31 and $K = l$

The result in Table2 indicates that AFC has the lowest value (3.08967) when the model specification is AFRIMA(1, d, 1) with $l(d = 0.07891)$. This implies that AFRIMA(1, d, 1) with $l(d = 0.07891)$ is more appropriate and has the best forecast performance compared to others. The significant is that AFRIMA(p, d, q) yields better forecasts as fractional integration gets closer to zero ($l(d \rightarrow 0)$). On the basis of our finding, we can otherwise say that, as $l(d \rightarrow 0.5)$ the poorer the AFRIMA forecast output becomes. The estimated model becomes

Table 3. AFRIMA Model Parameters

		Estimate	SE	t	Sig.	
Fractional Difference D=0.0789	Constant	19.330	.815	23.705	.000	
	AR	Lag 1	.901	.037	24.478	.000
	MA	Lag 1	-.073	.083	-.881	.379

$$\Delta^d x_t = 19.330 + 0.901\Delta^d x_{t-1} - 0.073\varepsilon_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (4)$$

p - val (0.000) (0.000) (0.379)

The constant and the AR parameters are significant under 5% level and the MA parameter is not significant.

Table4. Autocorrelation Test

Number of Predictors	Model Fit statistics	Ljung-Box Q(18)			Number of Outliers
	Stationary R-squared	Statistics	DF	Sig.	
0	.830	5.648	16	.991	0

The result of the Ljung-Box Chi-Square statistic indicates that the probability value(0.991) is not significant, hence, there is no autocorrelation in the residuals of the fitted model . Therefore, the AFRIMA(1, d, 1) is adequate.

Figure 6. The ACF Partial ACF of Residuals for AFRIMA (1, d, 1)

The ACF and partial ACF of residuals indicate that autocorrelation is not significant in the fitted model. Hence, the model is adequate and can be used to generate forecasts.

Table 5. Generated Forecast Using AFRIMA (1, d, 1) Model

Period	Forecast	Lower	Upper	Actual
167	18.5636	16.4932	20.6340	18.4280
168	18.6348	15.7372	21.5323	18.2110
169	18.6993	15.2689	22.1296	18.1502
170	18.7577	14.9453	22.5700	18.0457
171	18.8106	14.7113	22.9098	17.6507

The sample of forecast values generated using the long memory model is very close to the actual values. This means the AFRIMA (1, d, 1) can be used to study Naira-Yuan exchange rate dynamics for a better investment decision and risk management due to bilateral exchange rate uncertainties.

Figure7. The Observed and Fit Plot for Naira-Yuan Exchange Rate

The observed and fit plots are similar in pattern and dimension and the two values are very approximate. Therefore the fitted model is adequate.

Discussion of Findings

In our quest to compare different fractional integration in AFRIMA (p, d, q) forecast performance, the findings reveal that as fractional differencing varies towards zero, there is weak stationarity. This finding implies that the closer the value of ' d ' is to zero, the closer the fractional integration tends to $I(d=1)$. This is a scenario of near unit root and that explains the long memory nature of AFRIMA(p, d, q) model.

The model identification via ACF and PACF indicates AFRIMA(1, $d, 0$) and this identified model is compared with AFRIMA(1, $d, 1$) for different fractional integration using Amaefula forecast criterion (AFC). The result specifies that AFRIMA(1, $d, 1$) with $I(d = 0.07891)$ is more appropriate and has the best forecast performance compared to others. The previous research studies such as Onasanya and Adeniji(2013), Okon and Ikpang (2020) and Amaefula (2022, 2023) have devoted much attention on the ARIMA model. Hence, it becomes somewhat difficult to relate findings to literature reviewed.

The residual diagnostic test specifies model adequacy and forecast values are closely related to actual values.

CONCLUSION

The empirical results indicate that the AFRIMA model yield better and more precise forecasts when fractional integration is closer to zero, that is, $I(d \rightarrow 0)$ than when $I(d \rightarrow \frac{1}{2})$. However, the result also specifies that AFRIMA(1, $d, 1$) with $I(d = 0.07891)$ yield the best forecast for the Naira-Yuan exchange rate compared to others under study. Therefore, we conclude that when fractional integration is closer to zero, AFRIMA models can be useful in studying exchange rate dynamics for risk-averse and risk incline in times of investment and profitability.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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